

Table S2. Top scored compounds from each docking protocol screened using GOLD (CHEMPLP fitness scores) and DockThor (affinity, in kcal/mol).

Compound	CHEMPLP fitness	Affinity (kcal/mol)	Compound	CHEMPLP fitness	Affinity (kcal/mol)
BR010033	88.1441	-9.567	BR010669	78.1934	-7.943
BR010035	85.0729	-8.651	BR010672	80.3239	-7.734
BR010037	108.2236	-9.359	BR010673	85.1857	-7.896
BR010064	86.6541	-8.584	BR010696	83.3052	-8.075
BR010068	87.2800	-9.352	BR010697	78.5188	-7.209
BR010103	84.2271	-9.193	BR010704	62,4463	-8.797
BR010107	84.0879	-8.491	BR010705	62,4595	-8.658
BR010108	80.0736	-8.741	BR010706	60,7355	-8.881
BR010152	78.5479	-7.781	BR010708	69,8703	-8.381
BR010187	73.9342	-8.860	BR010714	65,7132	-8.455
BR010210	66.3679	-8.811	BR020113	72.2589	-9.057
BR010211	67.9674	-8.730	BR020119	66.4118	-8.318
BR010240	69.2982	-8.654	BR020126	63.7026	-8.261
BR010246	73.0318	-8.615	BR020127	69.9809	-8.146
BR010247	88.2998	-9.350	BR020128	81.9744	-8.620
BR010362	74.0993	-6.930	BR020201	45.6067	-8.347
BR010383	87.2368	-8.446	BR020251	55.1003	-8.370
BR010384	106.9992	-8.921	BR020253	56.6806	-8.323
BR010385	110.2038	-10.102	BR020254	49.4946	-8.610
BR010388	88.2070	-8.093	BR020255	79.9545	-9.097
BR010401	64.1276	-8.254	BR020323	72.0387	-9.157
BR010402	64.3036	-8.103	BR020325	82.7144	-9.107
BR010477	61.7335	-8.460	BR020337	64.3228	-9.069
BR010494	61.760	-8.397	BR020353	81.8051	-9.204
BR010497	61.8674	-8.495	BR020354	78.5539	-9.305
BR010565	69.8835	-8.533	BR020410	45.3855	-7.616
BR010574	76.4720	-8.928	BR020421	41.1823	-7.649
BR010576	76.1478	-8.497	BR020438	44.7177	-7.665
BR010595	72.8719	-8.640	BR020447	51.4656	-7.779
BR010597	71.3694	-8.880	BR020448	52.8194	-7.827